

PRODUCTS FORMED DURING THE PYROLYSIS PROCESS OF IRRADIATED PET WASTE

¹Gurbanov Muslum, ²Gulieva Ulviye, ³Elshen Mirzazada

^{1,2,3}Institute of Radiation Problems, Ministry of Science and Education, Baku, Azerbaijan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15430114>

Abstract. This research investigates the thermal decomposition process of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) plastic waste samples through gamma ionizing radiation and pyrolysis. PET plastic samples irradiated at different doses were subjected to pyrolysis at 550°C, and the gas, solid residue, and liquid product phases were analyzed. The results indicate that increasing radiation dose enhances gas yield, but at a certain dose threshold (794 kGy), the formation of a coal-like solid residue is observed. This suggests that the optimal radiation dose should be maintained between 794–900 kGy.

Keywords: PET, irradiation, pyrolysis, plastic waste, gas yield, thermal decomposition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plastic waste is one of the main sources of environmental problems, and developing new technologies for its management is crucial [1]. The thermal decomposition or pyrolysis of synthetic polymers such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET) provides a method to reduce waste while obtaining alternative energy sources [2]. However, the high thermal stability of PET makes its decomposition process challenging. Therefore, pre-irradiation of PET plastic material with ionizing radiation modifies its structure, making it more suitable for pyrolysis [3].

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the decomposition mechanism of polymer waste, particularly PET, using radiation and thermal pyrolysis methods. The pyrolysis and radiolysis processes of PET samples were compared, and the chemical composition and structural changes of the solid residues were analyzed using FTIR spectroscopy, EPR, and other analytical methods [4, 5].

2. METHODOLOGY

The samples were cut into small pieces with a surface area of approximately 0.03–0.06 mm² and a thickness of 1–2 mm, ensuring a moisture content of less than 10%. 0.5 g PET sample was irradiated in a Co-60 isotope facility within a dose range of 32–794 kGy. After irradiation, 0.03 g of the sample was subjected to pyrolysis at 550°C in a pyrolysis setup.

Figure 1. Scheme of pyrolysis equipment 1, 2-owns, 3-regulator

The gaseous products obtained from pyrolysis were analyzed using an Agilent 7890A gas chromatograph. The primary objective was to determine the ratios of hydrogen, methane, ethylene, and other fuel gases.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phase transformations of PET plastic samples during pyrolysis are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dependence of pyrolysis product yield of PET samples on adsorbed dose
Red line (Gas yield): The amount of gas increases steadily with dose, reaching a maximum at 794 kGy.

Green line (Liquid yield): The liquid amount decreases as the dose increases.

Blue line (Solid residue): Minimum at 32 kGy, then increases with higher doses.

As the radiation dose increases, the amount of the gas phase increases, the amount of the liquid phase decreases, and the amount of solid residue is at its minimum at 32 kGy but increases with higher doses. The gas yield from the initial PET sample pyrolysis was 0.16 g/g. However, as the radiation dose increased, the gas yield significantly increased, reaching a maximum of 0.41 g/g at 794 kGy. Additionally, the amount of solid residue increased, indicating the formation of carbon-like structures. The results suggest that an optimal dose of 794 kGy is required for maximizing gas yield, while a dose of 32–95 kGy is sufficient to minimize solid residue formation. Irradiation of PET waste with radiation enhances gas formation during pyrolysis. An optimal radiation dose of 794 kGy was identified for gas production, as higher doses lead to the formation of graphite-like solid residues. These results indicate that pre-irradiation of PET with ionizing radiation is beneficial for improving its decomposition through pyrolysis.

This study was conducted as part of the scientific research plan of the Institute of Radiation Problems of the Ministry of Science and Education and was supported by the IAEA within the framework of the project “Combined Radiation-Thermal Pyrolysis of Polymer Waste” (Grant No. F23036).

REFERENCES

1. Kumar J., Kannan T.T.M. Recycling of plastic waste into fuel by pyrolysis-a review. (2021), *Materials Today: Proceedings*, Volume 37, Part 2, p. 3718-3720. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.10.181>

2. Rajeev R., Muhammad A., Mohan J., Tuan N. Comprehensive Review on the Thermochemical Treatment of Plastic. (2025) *Materials Circular Economy* 7:3. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42824-024-00157-2>
3. José B. Parra¹, Conchi O. Ania¹, Ana Arenillas et al. Structural Changes in Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) Waste Materials Caused by Pyrolysis and CO₂ Activation. (2006) *Adsorption Science & Technology* Vol. 24 No. 5 DOI: 10.1260/026361706779849735
4. M.A.Gurbanov, R.J. Gasimov, M.A. Bayramov, Y.G. Hajieva, I.I. Mustafayev. EPR study of the effect of γ -irradiation on polypropylene/(CdS+ZnS) composites. (2024) *Problems of Atomic Science and Technology*, No.4 (152), pp. 29-33. <https://doi.org/10.46813/2024-152-0299>
5. Gurbanov, M. A., Gasimov, R. J., Bayramov, M. A., Guliyeva, U. A., & Mirzazada, E. V. Study of γ -irradiated polyethylene terephthalate polymer by EPR method. (2025). *Problems of Atomic Science and Technology*, 156(1), 25–40. <https://doi.org/10.46813/2025-156-0000>